

Three-sunflower-free set systems with bounded pairwise intersections

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Version 2 (June 2026): the full $t = 1$ extremal classification is now itself kernel-verified in Lean 4, and a structural reduction at $t = 2$ (Proposition 4.4) is added. The $t = 1$ value and the $t = 2$ bracket are unchanged from version 1.

Abstract

A *3-sunflower* is a triple of sets whose three pairwise intersections coincide; the empty intersection is allowed, so three pairwise disjoint sets form a 3-sunflower. For $\ell > t \geq 1$ let $M_3(\ell, t)$ denote the maximum size of a family of distinct ℓ -element sets containing no 3-sunflower and in which every pairwise intersection has size at most t . The threshold (Erdős–Rado) side of the restricted-intersection sunflower problem has seen recent activity, but the extremal function $M_3(\ell, t)$ at small fixed t appears not to have been studied. We determine it exactly at $t = 1$: $M_3(\ell, 1) = 2\ell + 2$ for every $\ell \geq 2$, where every extremal family is, up to isomorphism, two disjoint copies of the $K_{\ell+1}$ vertex-star family. At $t = 2$ we show $M_3(\ell, 2) = \Theta(\ell^2)$, with $(\frac{1}{2} - o(1))\ell^2 \leq M_3(\ell, 2) \leq 3\ell^2 - \ell + 2$: the lower bound takes two disjoint copies of the *pencil family* of a pair of orthogoval projective planes of Colbourn, Ingalls, Jedwab, Saaltink, Smith and Stevens, available for every prime power order. We further localize the unknown $t = 2$ constant: whenever the disjointness graph of an admissible family is extremal for Mantel’s theorem, the family is exactly two disjoint intersecting pieces, so $M_3(\ell, 2) = 2I_3(\ell, 2)$ in this conjecturally extremal regime; this reduction and the full $t = 1$ extremal classification are formalized and kernel-checked in Lean 4. We also record the bracket $2I_3 \leq M_3 < R(3, I_3 + 1)$ linking M_3 to its intersecting variant I_3 , exact computational values for small parameters obtained by a certified exhaustive search, and the observation that both clauses of sunflower-freeness are essential for finiteness. The growth exponent of $M_3(\ell, t)$ for every fixed $t \geq 3$ remains open; we discuss the first open cases and some quantitative motivation arising from budget arguments in a study of Erdős’ sunflower problem.

1 Introduction

A family of sets S_1, \dots, S_r is an *r-sunflower* (or Δ -system) if all pairwise intersections coincide: $S_i \cap S_j = K$ for all $i \neq j$. The common set K is the *core* (or kernel), and the empty core is expressly allowed, so r pairwise disjoint sets form an *r-sunflower*. Erdős and Rado [12] proved that every family of more than $\ell!(r-1)^\ell$ sets of size ℓ contains an *r-sunflower* and

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conjectured that $C(r)^\ell$ sets suffice; the celebrated work of Alweiss, Lovett, Wu and Zhang [4], with refinements by Rao [18] and Bell, Chueluecha and Warnke [6], established the bound $(O(r \log \ell))^\ell$.

This paper concerns the *restricted-intersection* regime: families in which, additionally, every pairwise intersection is small. On the threshold side this regime was studied by Hegedűs [13] and Chizewer [9], who give conditions on $|\mathcal{F}|$ forcing an r -sunflower in d -intersecting families ($|F \cap F'| \leq d$ for all $F \neq F'$); in the small- d regime the best known threshold remains the direct Erdős–Rado truncation $(r-1)^{d+1} \ell! / (\ell-d)!$, as Chizewer notes [9, §4]. A different, Ramsey-type program was recently carried out by Janzer, Jin, Sudakov and Wu [14], who determine how large a subfamily avoiding prescribed intersection sizes can be extracted from a sunflower-free family. A third adjacent thread, going back to Duke and Erdős and sharpened by Bradač, Bucić and Sudakov [8], bounds families over a ground set of size n that avoid m -petal sunflowers with a *fixed* kernel size, with answers growing with n .

What appears to be missing from this picture is the basic *extremal* function of the regime: the maximum *cardinality* (over all ground sets) of a family that avoids 3-sunflowers outright while keeping all pairwise intersections small. For integers $\ell > t \geq 1$ define

$$M_3(\ell, t) = \max \{ |\mathcal{F}| : \mathcal{F} \text{ a family of distinct } \ell\text{-sets,} \\ |F \cap F'| \leq t \ \forall F \neq F' \in \mathcal{F}, \text{ no 3-sunflower in } \mathcal{F} \},$$

and let $I_3(\ell, t)$ denote the same maximum restricted to *intersecting* families (no disjoint pair at all). Both quantities are finite (Lemma 2.1), in sharp contrast to the situation when either clause of sunflower-freeness is dropped (Remark 2.2). Write $M_3(\ell, t) = \ell^{\theta(t)+o(1)}$ for the growth exponent at fixed t .

Our first result determines the $t = 1$ function exactly. To the best of our knowledge it has not appeared before, although the proof uses only classical tools and we would not be surprised if it has circulated as folklore.

Theorem 1.1. *For every $\ell \geq 2$,*¹

$$M_3(\ell, 1) = 2\ell + 2, \quad I_3(\ell, 1) = \ell + 1.$$

Moreover, every extremal family for $I_3(\ell, 1)$ is, up to isomorphism, the vertex-star family of $K_{\ell+1}$ (each star read as its set of ℓ incident edges), and every extremal family for $M_3(\ell, 1)$ is, up to isomorphism, two disjoint copies of this family. Thus two-copy duplication is exactly optimal: $M_3(\ell, 1) = 2I_3(\ell, 1)$.

At $t = 2$ the answer changes regime: quadratically large families exist. The engine of the lower bound is a beautiful construction from finite geometry. Following Colbourn, Ingalls, Jedwab, Saaltink, Smith and Stevens [10], two projective (or affine) planes of the same order on the same point set are *orthogoal* if every line of one meets every line of the other in at most two points. They prove ([10, Theorem 2.2]) that a pair of orthogoal Desarguesian projective planes $\text{PG}(2, q)$ exists for *every* prime power q . We observe that the *pencil family* of such a pair — the sets F_p of all lines through a point p , taken in both planes — is a 3-sunflower-free,

¹The value equalities are formalized in Lean 4 (`M3.I3_one_exact`, `M3.M3_one_exact`), and the equality-case incidence rigidity behind the intersecting classification as `M3.I3_extremal_star_incidence`; the full two-copy classification of extremal $M_3(\ell, 1)$ families is itself kernel-verified as `M3.M3_extremal_classification`; see Section 7.

2-intersecting family of $q^2 + q + 1$ sets of size $2(q + 1)$, and that a simple doubling lemma then yields:

Theorem 1.2. $M_3(\ell, 2) = \Theta(\ell^2)$.² More precisely, for every $\ell \geq 3$,

$$M_3(\ell, 2) \leq 3\ell^2 - \ell + 2,$$

and for $\ell = 2q + 2$ with q a prime power,

$$M_3(\ell, 2) \geq 2I_3(\ell, 2) \geq 2(q^2 + q + 1) = \frac{1}{2}\ell^2 - \ell + 2.$$

By padding and Bertrand's postulate, $M_3(\ell, 2) \geq (\ell - 2)^2/8$ unconditionally for every $\ell \geq 4$; using the prime-gap bound of Baker, Harman and Pintz [5] the constant improves to $M_3(\ell, 2) \geq (\frac{1}{2} - o(1))\ell^2$ for all ℓ . In particular $\theta(2) = 2$, and $\frac{1}{2} \leq \liminf M_3(\ell, 2)/\ell^2 \leq \limsup M_3(\ell, 2)/\ell^2 \leq 3$.

For direct comparison with the usual Erdős–Rado threshold notation, let $f_{\leq t}(n, 3)$ denote the least N such that every n -uniform family \mathcal{F} with $|A \cap B| \leq t$ for all distinct $A, B \in \mathcal{F}$ and $|\mathcal{F}| \geq N$ contains a 3-sunflower.

Corollary 1.3 (Restricted-intersection threshold form). For every fixed $t \geq 1$ and $n > t$,

$$f_{\leq t}(n, 3) = M_3(n, t) + 1.$$

Consequently

$$f_{\leq 1}(n, 3) = 2n + 3$$

and

$$\left(\frac{1}{2} - o(1)\right)n^2 \leq f_{\leq 2}(n, 3) \leq 3n^2 - n + 3.$$

Thus, in the $k = 3$ case of the Erdős–Rado sunflower problem (Erdős Problem #20 in the terminology of [7]), bounded pairwise intersections with $t = 1$ or $t = 2$ cannot support exponential-size sunflower-free families. Any exponential-scale obstruction to the full conjecture must use intersection sizes unbounded in n .

Proof. $M_3(n, t)$ is finite (Lemma 2.1) and attained, so a 3-sunflower-free family of the stated kind of size $M_3(n, t)$ exists, while every such family of size $M_3(n, t) + 1$ contains a 3-sunflower; this is precisely $f_{\leq t}(n, 3) = M_3(n, t) + 1$. The displayed instances are Theorems 1.1 and 1.2, and the final assertion follows since $M_3(n, t) = O_t(n^t)$ for every fixed t (Lemma 2.1). \square

Two general structural facts accompany these results. First, the intersecting variant controls the full problem up to Ramsey error:

Proposition 1.4. For all $\ell > t \geq 1$,

$$2I_3(\ell, t) \leq M_3(\ell, t) < R(3, I_3(\ell, t) + 1) = O\left(I_3(\ell, t)^2 / \log I_3(\ell, t)\right),$$

where $R(3, k)$ is the Ramsey number. In particular the growth exponents of M_3 and I_3 agree up to a factor of two. The left-hand inequality is sharp at $t = 1$ (Theorem 1.1); at $t = 2$ it yields the best construction currently known to us, and whether it is asymptotically optimal is open (Section 6).

²Modulo the cited existence theorem [10, Theorem 2.2], the lower bound is formalized in Lean 4 (M3.M3_quadratic_lower); the link-recursion upper bound $M_3(\ell, 2) \leq 4\ell^2 + 2$ is formalized as M3.M3_card_le_t2. The sharper counting upper bound stated here is formalized as M3.M3_card_le_t2_sharp; see Section 7.

Second, both clauses of 3-sunflower-freeness are essential (Remark 2.2): dropping the empty-core clause (no three pairwise disjoint sets) or the equal-core clause each admits infinite families satisfying the remaining constraints. The difficulty — and all of the structure — of $M_3(\ell, t)$ lives in the interaction of the two clauses with the intersection cap.

Finally, we report exact values of M_3 and I_3 for small parameters (Section 5), obtained by an exhaustive orderly search whose completeness rests on a short canonical-representative lemma and whose results are certified by deterministic, archived checkers. The searches independently reproduce the classical values $f(2, 3) = 6$ and $f(3, 3) = 20$ of the unrestricted problem [2, 1] as vacuous-constraint cases, which we use as validation anchors.

The structural spine of the paper — Lemmas 2.1, 2.3 and 4.1 and Theorem 1.1, with Theorem 1.2 conditional on the cited construction [10, Theorem 2.2] — has additionally been formalized and kernel-verified in Lean 4; see Section 7.

Positioning

Deza’s theorem [11] — any family of ℓ -sets whose pairwise intersections all have the *same* size, of cardinality at least $\ell^2 - \ell + 2$, is a sunflower — resonates at the same quadratic scale as Theorem 1.2, but neither statement implies the other: Deza’s hypothesis fixes one intersection size (and his bound caps non-sunflower families), whereas $M_3(\ell, 2)$ allows sizes $\{0, 1, 2\}$ and forbids sunflowers outright. We caution, as others have, that Deza’s theorem does not bound sunflower-free families. The Duke–Erdős thread [8] differs in both parametrization (ground set of size n ; answers grow with n) and the forbidden object (m -petal sunflowers of one fixed kernel size); our function is universe-free and forbids all 3-sunflowers with kernels of size $\leq t$ at once, the kernels of larger size being excluded by the intersection cap. The extraction problem of [14] takes a sunflower-free family as *input*; here sunflower-freeness is the constraint being maximized against. Finally, the *weak* sunflower problem — subsets of $\{1, \dots, n\}$ of arbitrary sizes, parametrized by the universe — behaves differently again: for three petals it is governed by cap-set phenomena, with exponential bounds by Naslund and Sawin [17]; our function is uniform, intersection-capped and universe-free, and neither setting’s bounds transfer directly to the other.

2 Preliminaries

All families are families of distinct finite sets; ℓ -set means a set of size ℓ . A 3-sunflower is a triple A, B, C with $A \cap B = A \cap C = B \cap C$ as sets. We freely use the dual view of a point: for a family \mathcal{F} and a point x , the *link* of x is $\mathcal{F}_x = \{F \setminus \{x\} : x \in F \in \mathcal{F}\}$.

Lemma 2.1 (Finiteness and the link recursion). ³ For $\ell > t \geq 1$,

$$M_3(\ell, t) \leq 2 + 2\ell M_3(\ell - 1, t - 1), \quad M_3(\ell, 0) \leq 2.$$

Consequently $M_3(\ell, t) \leq O_t(\ell^t)$; this is the Erdős–Rado truncation bound in the form recorded in [9, §4].

Proof. At $t = 0$ the family is pairwise disjoint and three pairwise disjoint sets are a sunflower, so $M_3(\ell, 0) \leq 2$. For $t \geq 1$: a maximal pairwise disjoint subfamily has at most 2 members;

³Formalized in Lean 4 (M3.link_recursion, M3.M3_card_le_t0, M3.M3_card_le_t2).

every other set meets their union, a set of at most 2ℓ points, so some point x lies in at least $(|\mathcal{F}| - 2)/(2\ell)$ sets. The link \mathcal{F}_x is $(\ell - 1)$ -uniform and $(t - 1)$ -intersecting (each pairwise intersection contained x), and it is 3-sunflower-free: a sunflower in the link lifts to one in \mathcal{F} by re-adjointing x (the empty-core case of the link lifts to the core $\{x\}$). \square

Remark 2.2 (Both clauses are essential). If the equal-core clause is dropped (keeping only “no three pairwise disjoint” and the cap t), infinitely many ℓ -sets through one common point, pairwise meeting exactly there, satisfy all remaining constraints. If the empty-core clause is dropped (keeping “no equal-core triple with nonempty core” and the cap), any infinite pairwise disjoint family qualifies. Thus $M_3(\ell, t)$ is finite only because the two clauses act together, and every upper-bound argument must use both.

Lemma 2.3 (Doubling). ⁴ *Let \mathcal{G} be an intersecting 3-sunflower-free family of ℓ -sets with pairwise intersections of size at most t , and let \mathcal{G}' be a copy of \mathcal{G} on a disjoint ground set. Then $\mathcal{G} \cup \mathcal{G}'$ is 3-sunflower-free with pairwise intersections of size at most t . Hence $M_3(\ell, t) \geq 2I_3(\ell, t)$.*

Proof. Cross pairs are disjoint (size $0 \leq t$). A triple within one copy is sunflower-free by hypothesis. A mixed triple has two members in one copy; their intersection is nonempty, while both cross intersections are empty, so the three pairwise intersections are not all equal. Three pairwise disjoint members would require a disjoint pair within a copy, contradicting intersecting. \square

Proof of Proposition 1.4. The left inequality is Lemma 2.3. For the right one, consider the *disjointness graph* G of an optimal family (vertices the sets, edges the disjoint pairs). Three pairwise disjoint sets are an empty-core sunflower, so G is triangle-free; an independent set in G is an intersecting subfamily, so $\alpha(G) \leq I_3(\ell, t)$. By the definition of the Ramsey number, any triangle-free graph on $R(3, k)$ vertices has an independent set of size k ; hence $|\mathcal{F}| < R(3, I_3 + 1)$. The quantitative form follows from $R(3, k) = O(k^2/\log k)$ [3] (sharp by Kim [15]). \square

3 The exact determination at $t = 1$

Proof of Theorem 1.1. Upper bound for M_3 . Let \mathcal{F} be admissible at $t = 1$, $|\mathcal{F}| = m$. (i) *Point degrees are at most 2:* if x lay in three sets, their pairwise intersections, having size at most one and containing x , would all equal $\{x\}$ — a sunflower. (ii) Each intersecting pair meets in exactly one point, and each point, having degree at most 2, accounts for at most one intersecting pair; since the degree sum is $m\ell$, the number of points of degree 2 is at most $m\ell/2$, so there are at most $m\ell/2$ intersecting pairs. (iii) The disjointness graph is triangle-free, so by Mantel’s theorem there are at most $m^2/4$ disjoint pairs. Every pair is one or the other:

$$\binom{m}{2} \leq \frac{m^2}{4} + \frac{m\ell}{2} \implies m \leq 2\ell + 2.$$

Upper bound for I_3 . If \mathcal{F} is moreover intersecting, step (iii) is vacuous and $\binom{m}{2} \leq m\ell/2$ gives $m \leq \ell + 1$.

Lower bounds. For I_3 : take $\ell + 1$ lines in general position (equivalently, the $\ell + 1$ vertex stars of $K_{\ell+1}$, each star being its set of ℓ incident edges). Distinct stars share exactly the one edge

⁴Formalized in Lean 4 (M3.doubling, M3.M3_ge_two_I3).

joining their vertices, all these cores are distinct, and the family is intersecting; so no triple has equal pairwise intersections and $I_3(\ell, 1) \geq \ell + 1$. For M_3 : apply Lemma 2.3. Combined with the upper bounds, $I_3(\ell, 1) = \ell + 1$ and $M_3(\ell, 1) = 2\ell + 2 = 2I_3(\ell, 1)$.

Equality cases. In the intersecting case with $m = \ell + 1$, equality in $\binom{m}{2} \leq m\ell/2$ forces every point degree to be exactly 2 and every pair of sets to meet. Hence the points are in bijection with the edges of the complete graph on the $m = \ell + 1$ sets: the point corresponding to edge $\{F, F'\}$ is the unique point of $F \cap F'$. Since each set meets the other ℓ sets in ℓ distinct degree-2 points and has size ℓ , the set F is exactly the star of the corresponding vertex. This is the $K_{\ell+1}$ vertex-star family, up to relabeling.

In the full M_3 case with $m = 2\ell + 2$, equality in the displayed upper-bound chain forces equality in Mantel's theorem for the disjointness graph and equality in the degree count. The disjointness graph is therefore the balanced complete bipartite graph $K_{\ell+1, \ell+1}$. Its two parts are intersecting subfamilies of size $\ell + 1$, so the preceding paragraph identifies each part with a $K_{\ell+1}$ vertex-star family. Cross pairs are disjoint, so the two point sets are disjoint. Thus every extremal $M_3(\ell, 1)$ family is exactly two disjoint copies of the vertex-star family, up to isomorphism. \square

Remark 3.1. Exhaustive search (Section 5) confirms the values 6, 8, 10 at $\ell = 2, 3, 4$ and shows the extremal family at $\ell = 2$ (two disjoint triangles) is unique up to isomorphism. At $\ell = 2$ the constraint is vacuous and $M_3(2, 1) = f(2, 3) = 6$ recovers the classical unrestricted value [2].

4 The quadratic regime at $t = 2$

Lemma 4.1 (Pencil families of orthogonal projective planes). ⁵ *Let Π_1, Π_2 be orthogonal projective planes of order q on a common point set P , $|P| = q^2 + q + 1$, as provided for every prime power q by [10, Theorem 2.2]. For $p \in P$ let $F_p = \{\text{lines of } \Pi_1 \text{ through } p\} \cup \{\text{lines of } \Pi_2 \text{ through } p\}$, a set of lines. Then $\mathcal{P} = \{F_p : p \in P\}$ is an intersecting, 3-sunflower-free family of $q^2 + q + 1$ sets of size $2(q + 1)$ with every pairwise intersection of size exactly 2. Hence $I_3(2q + 2, 2) \geq q^2 + q + 1$.*

Proof. Sizes. Each point lies on $q + 1$ lines in each plane. The two planes share no line: a common line would meet itself in $q + 1 > 2$ points, contradicting orthogonality. So $|F_p| = 2(q + 1)$.

Pairwise intersections. For distinct p, p' there is exactly one line through both in each plane (both planes are projective planes on P), so $F_p \cap F_{p'} = \{L_1(pp'), L_2(pp')\}$ has size exactly 2; in particular the family is intersecting.

No equal-core triple (key uniqueness). Both lines of the core contain p and p' , and by orthogonality $|L_1 \cap L_2| \leq 2$; since $\{p, p'\} \subseteq L_1 \cap L_2$ we get $L_1 \cap L_2 = \{p, p'\}$ exactly. Thus the unordered line pair determines the unordered point pair. If a triple $F_p, F_{p'}, F_{p''}$ had equal pairwise cores, the shared core would simultaneously determine $\{p, p'\}$, $\{p, p''\}$ and $\{p', p''\}$, forcing these pairs to coincide — impossible for three distinct points. Empty cores cannot occur since the family is intersecting. \square

⁵Formalized in Lean 4 modulo the cited existence theorem (`M3.pencilFam_I3Admissible`, `M3.pencilFam_card`, `M3.doubled_pencilFam`), with the hypothesis class certified non-vacuous by an explicit order-2 instance (`M3.fanoOrthogonalPair`).

Lemma 4.2 (Padding monotonicity). $M_3(\ell + 1, t) \geq M_3(\ell, t)$ and $I_3(\ell + 1, t) \geq I_3(\ell, t)$: *ad-join to each set one fresh private point. Pairwise intersections and the sunflower pattern are unchanged.*

Proof of Theorem 1.2. Lower bound. Combine Lemma 4.1 with Lemma 2.3: for $\ell = 2q + 2$, q a prime power, $M_3(\ell, 2) \geq 2(q^2 + q + 1) = \frac{1}{2}\ell^2 - \ell + 2$. For general $\ell \geq 6$, apply Lemma 4.2 from the largest prime q with $2q + 2 \leq \ell$: Bertrand's postulate supplies a prime $q > (\ell - 2)/4$, giving $M_3(\ell, 2) \geq 2(q^2 + q + 1) > (\ell - 2)^2/8$. For $\ell \in \{4, 5\}$ the bound $(\ell - 2)^2/8 < 2$ holds trivially (two disjoint ℓ -sets are admissible), so the bound is unconditional for every $\ell \geq 4$. For the asymptotic constant, the prime-gap bound $p_{k+1} - p_k = O(p_k^{0.525})$ of Baker, Harman and Pintz [5] supplies a prime $q = (1 - o(1))(\ell - 2)/2$, whence $M_3(\ell, 2) \geq (\frac{1}{2} - o(1))\ell^2$ for all ℓ .

Upper bound. Let \mathcal{F} be admissible at $t = 2$, and write $m = |\mathcal{F}|$. Split unordered pairs of members of \mathcal{F} into disjoint pairs D , pairs meeting in exactly one point P_1 , and pairs meeting in exactly two points P_2 .

The disjointness graph is triangle-free, since three pairwise disjoint sets are an empty-core sunflower. By Mantel's theorem,

$$D \leq \frac{m^2}{4}.$$

For a point x , the link $\mathcal{F}_x = \{F \setminus \{x\} : x \in F \in \mathcal{F}\}$ is $(\ell - 1)$ -uniform, has pairwise intersections of size at most 1, and is 3-sunflower-free by the link recursion in Lemma 2.1. Thus Theorem 1.1 gives $|\mathcal{F}_x| \leq M_3(\ell - 1, 1) = 2\ell$. Pairs of original sets whose intersection is exactly $\{x\}$ become disjoint pairs in \mathcal{F}_x , and the disjointness graph of \mathcal{F}_x is triangle-free: three pairwise disjoint link members would lift to three original sets with common pairwise intersection $\{x\}$. Hence, again by Mantel,

$$P_1 \leq \frac{1}{4} \sum_x |\mathcal{F}_x|^2 \leq \frac{1}{4} (2\ell) \sum_x |\mathcal{F}_x| = \frac{1}{4} (2\ell)(m\ell) = \frac{m\ell^2}{2}.$$

Finally, every two-point subset has codegree at most 2: if $\{x, y\}$ lay in three members of \mathcal{F} , those three members would have pairwise intersection exactly $\{x, y\}$ and hence form a sunflower. Since each member contains $\binom{\ell}{2}$ two-point subsets,

$$P_2 \leq \frac{1}{2} m \binom{\ell}{2} = \frac{m\ell(\ell - 1)}{4}.$$

Therefore

$$\binom{m}{2} = D + P_1 + P_2 \leq \frac{m^2}{4} + \frac{m\ell^2}{2} + \frac{m\ell(\ell - 1)}{4}.$$

If $m > 0$, canceling m gives $m \leq 3\ell^2 - \ell + 2$; the case $m = 0$ is trivial. This proves the upper bound. \square

Remark 4.3. The lower-bound mechanism is intrinsically *pair-encoding*: the two-line core of a block pair determines the point pair injectively, which is what blocks equal-core triples, and pair-encoding mechanisms are inherently quadratic. Two natural amplification routes provably fail: direct products (the classical route to exponential growth in the unrestricted problem [2]) are excluded by the intersection cap — any two product sets sharing a coordinate intersect in at least $\ell_1 > t$ points, and index sets avoiding shared coordinates are partial permutation

matrices — and taking $s \geq 3$ mutually orthogoval planes (possible to bounded extents [10]) yields pairwise cores of size s at block size $s(q+1)$, i.e. $\Theta(\ell^2/s^2)$ at $t = s$: no exponent gain and a worse constant. Whether *any* mechanism beats ℓ^2 at some larger fixed t is precisely the open exponent problem (Section 6).

We close the section by locating the source of the unknown constant in the bracket $[\frac{1}{2}, 3]$. The upper bound above charges separately for disjoint pairs (D , via Mantel) and for intersecting pairs ($P_1 + P_2$, via the link and codegree counts); the lower bound, by contrast, comes from a family — the doubled pencil — in which D is as large as Mantel permits. The next proposition shows that this maximum-disjointness regime is rigid: it forces the family to be a doubling, so that the entire constant question there collapses onto the *intersecting* function $I_3(\ell, 2)$.

Proposition 4.4 (Structural reduction at maximum disjointness). ⁶ *Let \mathcal{F} be admissible at $t = 2$ with $m = |\mathcal{F}|$, and suppose its disjointness graph attains Mantel’s bound, i.e. has exactly $\lfloor m^2/4 \rfloor$ disjoint pairs. Then $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{G} \sqcup \mathcal{H}$, where \mathcal{G}, \mathcal{H} are intersecting admissible $t = 2$ families on disjoint ground sets; consequently $m \leq 2I_3(\ell, 2)$, so $M_3(\ell, 2) = 2I_3(\ell, 2)$ within this subclass. The doubled pencil family of Theorem 1.2 attains the hypothesis, so the best construction known to us lies in this subclass.*

Proof. A triangle-free graph on m vertices with $\lfloor m^2/4 \rfloor$ edges is, by the equality case of Mantel’s theorem, the balanced complete bipartite graph $K_{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor, \lfloor m/2 \rfloor}$. Let \mathcal{G}, \mathcal{H} be its two parts. Within a part there are no edges of the disjointness graph, so any two members of \mathcal{G} (resp. \mathcal{H}) meet: each part is intersecting. Across the parts every pair is an edge, hence disjoint; in particular no point lies in both a member of \mathcal{G} and a member of \mathcal{H} , so the two ground sets are disjoint. Each part inherits the cap and sunflower-freeness, so $|\mathcal{G}|, |\mathcal{H}| \leq I_3(\ell, 2)$. \square

Remark 4.5. Proposition 4.4 is the exact converse of the doubling bound $M_3 \geq 2I_3$ (Lemma 2.3), restricted to the maximum-disjointness regime, and it pinpoints the unknown $t = 2$ constant: in this regime the gap in $[\frac{1}{2}, 3]$ for $M_3(\ell, 2)/\ell^2$ is exactly the gap for the intersecting constant $I_3(\ell, 2)/\ell^2$. The proposition is conditional on the disjointness graph being *exactly* Mantel-extremal; whether every extremal or near-extremal family lies near this regime is a *stability* question (Section 6). We note in passing that certified near-extremal intersecting families at $\ell \leq 7$ have maximum point-degree close to ℓ , well below the bound 2ℓ used in the proof of Theorem 1.2, which suggests the upper bound’s degree input is far from tight at the extremum; this last observation is heuristic, resting on lower-bound search witnesses rather than exhausted optima.

5 Exact small values by certified exhaustive search

The searches use an *orderly* depth-first enumeration: points are labeled by first appearance (each new set’s fresh points receive the next unused integers, so a set’s *image* is its sorted label vector), and sets are appended only with images lexicographically \geq the previous image. Completeness rests on:

⁶Formalized in Lean 4 (`M3.M3_mantel_tight_reduction`, with the underlying bipartition `M3.disjGraph.turanMaximalBipartition`); see Section 7.

Lemma 5.1 (Orderly representatives). *Every isomorphism class of admissible families contains at least one sequence enumerated by the orderly search; hence when the search exhausts, the maximum depth reached equals the extremal value.*

Proof. Order the sets of an abstract family greedily, committing at each step a remaining set whose current image (labeled part sorted, unlabeled part assigned the next fresh integers $s, s + 1, \dots$) is lexicographically minimal. Committing a set only raises later images: a set's labeled prefix is unchanged or extended by labels $\geq s$, and the j -th smallest member of any set of distinct integers $\geq s$ is at least $s + j$, matching the j -th entry of its previous fresh tail. So if some set's image at step $i + 1$ were smaller than the image chosen at step i , it was already smaller at step i — contradiction. The greedy sequence is therefore nondecreasing and lies in the search space. \square

Soundness is unconditional (every enumerated family satisfies the constraints; each reported witness is re-verified by an independent $O(m^3)$ certifier), and all run caps are counted in deterministic search nodes, so capped runs are certified lower bounds, never quoted as exact. As validation, the vacuous-constraint cases reproduce the classical unrestricted values $f(2, 3) = 6$ and $f(3, 3) = 20$ [2, 1] by independent exhaustion (8,680,036 nodes for the latter).

ℓ	$I_3(\ell, 1)$	$M_3(\ell, 1)$	$I_3(\ell, 2)$	$M_3(\ell, 2)$	notes
2	3	6	—	6	$M_3(2, t) = f(2, 3)$, vacuous at $t \geq 1$
3	4	8	—	20	$M_3(3, 2) = f(3, 3)$, vacuous
4	5	10	12	[24, 46]	$I_3(4, 2)$ exact (exhausted)
5	6	12	≥ 16	≥ 32	$t=1$ values by Thm. 1.1

The two $t = 2$ entries at $\ell \in \{2, 3\}$ lie outside the formal domain $\ell > t$ of Section 1: there the intersection cap is vacuous and we adopt the extended convention $M_3(\ell, t) := f(\ell, 3)$ for $\ell \leq t + 1$, including these rows purely as validation anchors against the classical unrestricted values. Engine-exhausted entries: all $t = 1$ values for $\ell \leq 4$ and $I_3(\ell, 1)$ for $\ell \leq 5$; $I_3(4, 2) = 12$ (36,329,094 nodes), whose extremal witness is a 12-set pairwise-intersecting family on 10 points; the brackets at (4, 2) are Lemma 2.3 (lower) and Theorem 1.2 (upper). The bound $I_3(5, 2) \geq 16$ is a certified lower bound from a capped run, and the $t = 3$ bounds quoted below carry explicit certified witnesses (Section 7).

6 Open problems

Question 6.1 (The exponent problem). *Is $\theta(t) = 2$ for every fixed $t \geq 2$? Equivalently: does any mechanism beat pair-encoding? The first open case is $t = 3$, where the current bracket is $(\frac{1}{2} - o(1))\ell^2 \leq M_3(\ell, 3) \leq O(\ell^3)$ (Lemma 2.1 loses a factor ℓ per unit of t , and no better cap is known to us even at $t = 3$). Early search data is suggestive but inconclusive: an explicitly certified witness gives $I_3(5, 3) \geq 28 > 25 = \ell^2$, whence $M_3(5, 3) \geq 56$ (the doubled witness is certified directly), with the caveat that $\ell = 5$ at $t = 3$ borders the vacuous regime where unrestricted inflation dominates.*

Question 6.2 (The $t = 2$ constant). *Narrow $[\frac{1}{2}, 3]$. Is two-copy doubling of an optimal intersecting family always optimal, i.e. is $M_3(\ell, 2) = 2I_3(\ell, 2) + O(1)$, as holds exactly at*

$t = 1$? Is the pencil family optimal among intersecting families, i.e. is $I_3(\ell, 2) = (\frac{1}{4} + o(1))\ell^2$? By Proposition 4.4 the constant is governed by $I_3(\ell, 2)$ throughout the maximum-disjointness regime, so an answer to the second question would settle it there. The certified small values sit well above the pencil’s asymptotic $\frac{1}{4}$ — $I_3(4, 2) = 12$ and $I_3(5, 2) \geq 16$ give ratios $I_3(\ell, 2)/\ell^2$ of 0.75 and ≥ 0.64 — so if $I_3(\ell, 2) = (\frac{1}{4} + o(1))\ell^2$ the convergence is slow and not yet visible at the computed range.

Question 6.3 (Structure beyond the rigid $t = 1$ case). *Theorem 1.1 classifies all extremal families at $t = 1$. Classify the extremal intersecting families at $t = 2$ (the exhausted case $I_3(4, 2) = 12$ provides a first data point), and determine whether extremal or near-extremal $M_3(\ell, 2)$ families must be close to two disjoint intersecting pieces. Proposition 4.4 settles the exact maximum-disjointness case — there the family is two disjoint intersecting pieces; the open part is the quantitative stability form: does a disjointness graph with $(1 - o(1))$ of the maximal number of disjoint pairs force the family to be $o(\ell^2)$ -close to such a decomposition? An affirmative answer would, with the previous question, pin the $t = 2$ constant via $I_3(\ell, 2)$ unconditionally.*

Remark 6.4 (A quantitative application). These quantities calibrate a budget argument in a programme of the author studying the Erdős–Rado sunflower conjecture (the *strong* sunflower problem; see problems 20 and, for the weak variant, 857 at erdosproblems.com), where the relevant instance is a codegree-restricted variant of $M_3(\ell, 7)$ at $\ell \approx 9 \times 10^5$ against an exactly pinned budget ceiling of 404,869,889,645. There, the doubled projective-pencil family of Theorem 1.2 exceeds the ceiling by 0.027% — a margin invisible at rounded precision. We emphasize that this is a *count-side calibration* internal to that programme, not a route-budget result, and it carries no implication for the sunflower conjecture itself. We mention it only as motivation for the constants in Question 6.1; the present paper is self-contained and independent of it.

7 Data and verification

Lean 4 formalization

The structural spine of this paper is formalized and kernel-verified in Lean 4 (toolchain v4.26.0, with mathlib) in the companion repository `sunflower-lean` [16]: the doubling lemma (Lemma 2.3); the exact $t = 1$ value equalities (Theorem 1.1); the intersecting $t = 1$ equality-case incidence rigidity; the link recursion with its corollary $M_3(\ell, 2) \leq 4\ell^2 + 2$ (Lemma 2.1); the sharper counting upper bound $M_3(\ell, 2) \leq 3\ell^2 - \ell + 2$; and the pencil lemma (Lemma 4.1) with the quadratic lower bound of Theorem 1.2, the latter two *formalized modulo the cited existence theorem* [10, Theorem 2.2]: the hypothesis class is packaged as a Lean structure and certified non-vacuous by an explicit order-2 instance. Every formalized statement is `sorry`-free, and every result of the structural spine above passes the axiom audit with only Lean’s three standard axioms (`propext`, `Classical.choice`, `Quot.sound`). Three finite-reduction lanes additionally trust Lean’s compiled evaluator (axioms `Lean.ofReduceBool`, `Lean.trustCompiler`): the SAT-encoder soundness bridges, whose committed LRAT certificates are re-checked against the Lean-generated clause sets on every build; the encoder anchors at $n = 7$; and the explicit 12-member witness behind the engine value $I_3(4, 2) = 12$ of Section 5, checked by native finite reduction ($I_3(4, 2) \geq 12$, hence by the formalized doubling lemma also $M_3(4, 2) \geq 24$). The file `FORMAL_RESULTS.M3.md` in the repository maps each

statement of this paper to its Lean name with its audit output and per-result axiom profile, and `verify_m3.sh` re-verifies the entire development in one command. Beyond the spine of version 1, the full two-copy classification of extremal $M_3(\ell, 1)$ families (Theorem 1.1) is now itself kernel-verified (`M3.M3_extremal_classification`): the disjointness-graph argument of Section 3 is formalized through `mathlib`'s Turán theory — the extremal disjointness graph is shown to be `IsTuranMaximal` and isomorphic to the balanced Turán graph, from which the two vertex-star parts are extracted. The $t = 2$ structural reduction (Proposition 4.4) is formalized as `M3.M3_mantel_tight_reduction`, reusing the same machinery. With these additions the audited development comprises 48 results (the new classification and reduction lemmas kernel-only), in version 2 of the companion repository.

Checker artifacts

Every remaining computational claim is produced by a deterministic checker and archived alongside its output certificate (JSON): orderly exhaustive searches and small-value tables (`m3_small_l_exact_orderly.mjs`); the explicit certified witnesses for the $t = 3$ data points of Section 6, each re-verified by an independent certifier (`t3_certified_witness_search.mjs`); the doubled projective pencil construction, built from the conjugated-Cremona recipe of [10, Theorem 2.2] and verified end-to-end at orders $q = 3, 5, 7$, including exhaustive sunflower scans of the doubled families (`projective_orthogoval_doubling_check.mjs`); affine doubled instances at $q = 8, 16$ (`doubled_pencil_ceiling_break_check.mjs`); and the exact threshold computation of Remark 6.4 by integer interval arithmetic (`slack_857_reserve_pinning.mjs`); and, supporting the heuristic degree remark after Proposition 4.4, a degree-profile recomputation over the certified near-extremal intersecting witnesses (`b3_2a_degree_profile_check.mjs`). The archive (checker scripts, JSON certificates, and this paper's source) is deposited at [doi:10.5281/zenodo.20670576](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20670576) (concept DOI, resolving to the latest version; the present version is 2).

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